

Strategic landscape reconfiguration to limit wildfire hazard in southwestern France : A simulation approach

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Abstract

Extreme fire events are becoming increasingly frequent in southwestern France as a result of anthropogenic climate change, with the Landes de Gascogne, Europe's largest contiguous pine plantation, showing growing vulnerability to large, fast-moving wildfires. This study evaluates how projected climatic conditions and strategic landscape reorganization influence burn probability across the Gironde and Landes departments. Using the Burn-P3+ fire simulation system, we conducted 20,000 fire-spread simulations per scenario at 30-m resolution under three Fire Weather Index (FWI)-driven climatic conditions: a historical "Moderate" scenario (1991–2020), a recent "High" scenario (2021–2022), and a future "Extreme" scenario (2041–2070).

Results show a clear increase in burn probability from Moderate to High and Extreme scenarios, reflecting the strengthening of fire-conducive meteorological conditions. High-probability zones are consistently concentrated in areas dominated by immature maritime pine stands. In contrast, landscape reorganization substantially reduces burn probability, particularly under Extreme conditions.

These findings highlight the dominant role of climatic forcing in shaping wildfire hazard in homogeneous productive pine landscapes, while demonstrating that strategic spatial restructuring of low-fuel areas can mitigate burn probability even under severe climatic extremes. This work underscores the value of landscape-scale planning as a complementary strategy to conventional fuel treatments and provides actionable insights for enhancing wildfire resilience in the Landes de Gascogne under future climate conditions.

Introduction

Climate change requires to think further fire-risk management

The increasing frequency of extreme weather events (EWEs) such as prolonged droughts, heatwaves, and intense wildfires represents significant challenges for forest management in Europe (IPCC, 2021; Dupuy et al., 2020). These events, exacerbated by climate change, contribute to an increased likelihood of catastrophic wildfires that threaten human lives, ecosystems, and economies (Bowman et al., 2020). In several parts of Mediterranean Europe historically shaped by frequent, low-intensity fires, fire activity has declined over the past few decades due to active suppression, landscape change, and prevention measures (Pausas & Keeley, 2009; Curt et al., 2016). However, this pattern is not uniform across the region, as some dense shrublands (e.g., maquis, garrigue) have long experienced high-intensity fire regimes. However, in other areas, particularly in southern Europe, fire suppression combined with vegetation regrowth on abandoned agricultural land and increasing anthropogenic pressures has led to the accumulation of fuel loads and highly flammable landscapes. As a result, wildfire activity has increased in recent years, leading to extreme and uncontrollable fire events further amplified by exceptional meteorological conditions (Moreira et al., 2010; Ganteaume et al., 2013; Higuera et al., 2015).

Parts of southwest France, however, present a different dynamic, where fire suppression remains largely effective due to the intensive management of pine plantations and well-developed firefighting infrastructures made roads and water points (Valette et al., 2019). This area, known as the Landes de Gascogne, situated mainly in the Landes and Gironde departments of France, represents the second-largest commercial forest area in Europe, after the fennoscandian region. While the current fire-management system has been largely effective at limiting the occurrence of large, damaging wildfires, it has been increasingly challenged in recent years by the emergence of larger and more extreme fire events driven by compounding weather extremes and rapidly changing conditions. In this context, the FIRE-RES project, were put forward to develop resilient forest and landscape-management strategies that mitigate extreme wildfire risks while enhancing the adaptive capacity of landscapes

under changing climatic conditions. FIRE-RES is a European-funded initiative that integrates research, operational tools, and stakeholder engagement to improve fire prevention, suppression, and post-fire recovery. One of its key objectives is to test innovative fire management approaches through Living Labs (LLs), where real-world case studies are used to co-develop and implement adaptive strategies.

The Nouvelle-Aquitaine Living Lab (LL AQT) encompasses two of France's most fire-prone departments: Gironde and Landes. The devastating 2022 wildfire season in the region, driven by record-breaking drought and heatwave conditions not observed in over 50 years (Météo-France, 2022), underscored the urgency of developing effective fire management tools. The two wildfires in Landiras and La Teste-de-Buch burned over 27,000 hectares, highlighting the limitations of current suppression efforts in the face of extreme weather conditions and high, continuous fuel loads. Large wildfires are not unprecedented in the area; for example, a fire in 1949 killed 82 people and prompted major changes to fire-management policies and practices (e.g., Papy, 1950; Bodet, 1951). In fact, the wildfire potential of this highly forested area has been recognized for decades (Parisien et al. 2018) and is likely to be amplified if future wildfire projections are borne out. Recent attribution studies have demonstrated that the extreme 2022 wildfire season in southwest France was made significantly more likely by anthropogenic climate change (Lanet et al., 2024). Moreover, future climate projections indicate a substantial increase in the frequency and intensity of fire-conducive weather conditions in the region, with marked rises in FWI-driven danger days and compounding drought-heatwave events expected over the coming decades (Lanet et al., 2025). Together, these findings reinforce the need for forward-looking fire-risk management strategies capable of addressing unprecedented levels of climatic pressure on the Landes de Gascogne forest system.

To address these challenges and improve preparedness to extreme fires of the most productive maritime pine forest of France this study propose advanced fire simulations and a high resolution fuel map to assess wildfire behavior under extreme weather conditions. While meteorologically driven fire danger indices such as those of the Fire Weather Index (FWI) System provide essential daily assessments of fire danger for

wildfire operations (Van Wagner, 1987), they do not provide quantitative measures of fire behavior, nor do they account for the spatial dynamics of wildfire ignitions and spread. Dynamic fire simulation software, such as Burn-P3+ using the PROMETHEUS model, which incorporate key variables like fuel characteristics, topography, and meteorological conditions, enable a more comprehensive evaluation of fire behavior at the landscape scale (Finney, 2005; Parisien et al., 2005). These simulation-based tools have proven highly effective in North America, southern Europe, and Australia for informing fire prevention strategies and scenario-based landscape management (Ager et al., 2010; Oliveira et al., 2016).

The adaptation of Canadian fire-management methodologies based on the Canadian Forest Fire Behavior Prediction (FBP) System (PCI), which provides quantitative measures of fire behavior based on weather, flammable vegetation (i.e., fuels), and topography, presents an additional opportunity for improving fire preparedness in Nouvelle-Aquitaine, particularly in Gironde and Landes. This method, which has been operational for decades across Canada (Forestry Canada Fire Danger Group 1992), was deemed suitable for fire-hazard analysis in the Nouvelle-Aquitaine region. Local fire agencies have already adopted and adapted the Canadian Forest Fire Danger Rating System (CFFDRS) to evaluate fire ignition potential and deploy firefighting resources on a daily basis (Météo-France, 2022). Moreover, the forest structures in Gironde and Landes, dominated by the maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster*), resemble Canadian pine forests, where fire behavior is well-documented and represented in the FBP System fuels (Van Wagner, 1989; Stocks et al., 2004; Rigolot & Fernandes, 2005). This structural similarity provides a robust foundation for adapting dynamic fire modeling approaches, particularly in addressing the crown fire risks inherent to these forest landscapes.

In addition to assessing current and future fire behavior, we also sought to evaluate whether modifying the spatial arrangement of low-fuel areas could reduce landscape-scale wildfire risk under extreme weather conditions. This concept, which we refer to here as a form of landscape reorganization, consists of strategically redistributing fuel-discontinuous zones (e.g., agricultural areas, young stands, water bodies, managed fuel breaks) to create compartmentalized fuel cells. The underlying hypothesis is that a

more efficient spatial configuration of these low-fuel features, functionally similar to fuel treatments or vegetation management, may help constrain fire spread during large, fast-moving wildfire events by disrupting continuity and reducing the potential for long-distance runs. Testing this idea provides insight into whether landscape-level planning, beyond stand-scale fuel treatments, can offer measurable benefits in fire scenarios typical of future climate conditions.

This study aims to :

- Assess the impact of climate change on fire hazard in Landes of Gascony in term of probability of fire
- Evaluate the effectiveness of **landscape reorganization in reducing wildfire risks in Gironde and Landes under extreme weather conditions.**
- Build a complete risk map by incorporating urban exposure and delineate fireheds and zone most a risk requiring immediate actions

Study Area

The study area covers the departments of Gironde and Landes in southwestern France, located within the Nouvelle-Aquitaine region. This area is particularly fire-prone due to its extensive plantation forests, dominated by maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster*), interspersed with oak species (*Quercus robur*, *Q. pyrenaica*, *Q. suber*) and heathland. These vegetation types form large, continuous fuel beds capable of sustaining intense fire behavior under extreme weather conditions (Gascogne Bois, 2024).

Climatically, the region has a temperate maritime regime with mild, wet winters and warm summers. Recent assessments indicate a sharp increase in fire risk: rising temperatures, more frequent and prolonged droughts, and stronger wind patterns have all contributed to conditions that favor rapid fire spread (Nouvelle-Aquitaine Strategic Environmental Assessment, 2022; ATMO Nouvelle-Aquitaine, 2023).

Historically, the landscape has been shaped by intensive forestry. The Landes de Gascogne massif is largely composed of monoculture maritime pine plantations,

increasing both fuel continuity and homogeneity (Mauge, 1984). This forestry structure, combined with modern land use, has fundamentally altered the natural fire regime, making large canopy fires more likely and harder to control.

On the operational side, local fire management agencies use an adapted version of the Canadian Forest Fire Danger Rating System (FFDRS) to assess daily ignition potential and guide suppression efforts. However, the growing frequency and severity of extreme fire events call into question the long-term sustainability of existing fire management strategies (Gironde Département, 2025).

This region was chosen for simulation not only because of its high fire susceptibility, but also because its forest structure and management practices make it ideal for testing the applicability of advanced fire simulation tools and for designing landscape-level strategies to increase fire resilience.

Figure 1. Study area in Landes de Gascogne, Gironde and Landes department

Materials and Methods

This study aims to evaluate wildfire dynamics in the Gironde and Landes departments under extreme weather conditions, providing insights for fire risk management and landscape planning in southwestern France. The methodology integrates climate scenarios, land-use variations, and advanced fire simulation modeling.

Study Data

Several datasets were used to characterize the study area and support simulations:

- Climatic data : Meteorological variables for the study area were sourced from Météo-France, including temperature, precipitation, wind, and humidity for recent extreme fire seasons (e.g., 2022). These data were used to define fire weather scenarios representing varying levels of hazard.
- Vegetation and fuel data : Two fuel maps were employed: (i) the actual 2023 fuel map used by firefighting services, representing current landscape conditions, and (ii) a modified map with strategic land-use adjustments creating fuel interruptions by reorganizing low-fuel areas while maintaining overall land-use ratios.
- Forest and landscape characteristics : Spatial data describing forest types, topography, and human assets (IGN building map) were integrated to analyse fire behaviour and potential stakes.

Climatic scenarios

Wildfire likelihood was assessed under three fire-weather scenarios: moderate, high, and extreme. These scenarios reflect increasing levels of fire danger and were designed to capture potential variations in meteorological conditions, including heatwaves, prolonged drought, and strong winds. The scenario inputs were incorporated into BURN-P3 to simulate fire spread and behaviour, with a particular focus on large fires under extreme conditions.

Table 1. Description of weather scenarios as input of BURN P3+

Scenario	Description	Reference weather data
Moderate	Characterized by moderate FWI (Fire Weather Index) values.	Use 1991-2020 ERA5 data in Landes de Gascogne as reference
High	Representing conditions at the upper range of FWI, with a focus on extreme fire behavior based on 2022 events	Use 2021-2022 ERA5 data in Landes de Gascogne
Extreme	Predicting what conditions could encounter the study area in the future based on GIEC models	Use 2041-2070 ERA5 projection data in Landes de Gascogne

The scenarios' inputs were integrated into the BURN-P3 tool to simulate fire spread and behaviour, particularly focusing on large fires under extreme conditions.

Land-use scenarios

To evaluate the influence of landscape configuration on wildfire hazard, the study compared simulations using two fuel maps (Figure 2). First, the current 2023 fuel map, representing the actual landscape used by firefighting services, reflecting existing vegetation types, forest structure, and fuel distribution. Then, the strategically reorganized fuel map, designed to test the hypothesis that the spatial arrangement of low-fuel areas can influence wildfire behaviour at the landscape scale. This map maintains the same overall land-use proportions as the current map but realigns low-fuel areas into continuous corridors across the landscape.

The idea behind this scenario is not to remove forest or reduce forest cover, but rather to explore whether a strategic spatial distribution of low-fuel areas could act as landscape-scale firebreaks, potentially interrupting fire propagation and enhancing management effectiveness. By leveraging existing low-fuel patches (e.g., roads, young stands, shrublands), these corridors aim to create structural discontinuities in the fuel network without altering the overall composition of the landscape.

This approach directly addresses the study's specific objective : to evaluate the effectiveness of landscape reorganization in reducing wildfire risks in Gironde and Landes under extreme weather conditions. By comparing fire behaviour outcomes under the current and reorganized scenarios, the study assesses the potential benefits and limitations of proactive landscape design as a complementary measure to conventional firefighting efforts.

Fire Simulation Tool

The PROMETHEUS fire simulation model was implemented through the BURN-P3+ software (Parisien et al., 2005) to simulate wildfire behavior and evaluate fire management strategies under different weather scenarios in the study area. This probabilistic model integrates fire spread algorithms with spatial and statistical analyses, allowing researchers to estimate wildfire likelihood across heterogeneous landscapes. Using Monte Carlo processes, BURN-P3+ simulates the ignition and propagation of a large number of fires on an hourly basis over a full year, typically representing the upcoming fire season. This simulated year is then repeated thousands of times to account for the stochastic nature of fire ignitions and the variability of meteorological conditions, providing a robust probabilistic assessment of fire behavior under diverse environmental and climatic scenarios.

Input data

The fuel map represents vegetation and land-cover characteristics relevant to fire behavior modeling and was compiled from multiple national and regional datasets:

- GIP ATGeRi: land-use stabilization polygons
- SDIS 33 and SDIS 40: fuel mitigation zones
- IGN – BD Forêt® v2 & MNT 2023: forest type, stand structure, and terrain derivatives
- IFN (Inventaire Forestier National): forest structural attributes

Topographic information was derived from the IGN BD-ALTI® 30 m digital elevation model, which provides nationwide coverage with a spatial resolution of 30 m and vertical accuracy suitable for regional-scale fire spread simulations (IGN, 2023).

Landscape input data were resampled to match the fuel map grid to ensure spatial consistency across all model inputs (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Landscape input data. Fuel map, Digital elevation model (DEM), Weather zones and Ignition grid used for BURN-P3+ simulations (sources: GIP ATGeRi, IGN BD-ALTI® 30 m resolution, INRAE).

Vegetation classes from southwestern France were interpreted and translated into Fuel types of the Canadian FBP System following the methodology proposed by Parisien et al. (2018) for adapting FBP fuel types to European pine-dominated landscapes. Each fuel class was assigned:

- an equivalent FBP fuel type,
- its curing parameters,
- relevant structural attributes (canopy cover, surface fuel load, understory type).

All fuel types according to the FBP System, with their related curing parameters depending on vegetation, are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1. Vegetation types descriptions and equivalent fuel types based on FBP System

Vegetation type	Fuel category (PCI estimate)	Fuel map code
<i>Maritime pine : 1 to 25 years after reforestation</i>	O-1-1 (grass and young pines)	4
<i>Herbaceous surfaces (meadows, non-agricultural grasslands, pastures and lawns, dyked areas) and orchards</i>	O-1-2	31
<i>Maritime pine (plantation): 26 years and more</i>	C-3 (mature jack pine or lodgepole pine)	3
<i>Riparian vegetation (alder and oak)</i>	D-1/2 (aspen)	13
<i>Damage area (uncleared) and landfills</i>	S-1 (jack pine or lodgepole pine slash)	21
<i>Mixed oak (mostly maritime pine)</i>	M-1/2 (25% coniferous) (mixed boreal forest)	625
<i>Recently ploughed fields Irrigated fields (agriculture) Rocks, lakes, rivers, urban areas</i>	Non-fuel	101

Ignition probability inputs were produced by INRAE using historical wildfire ignition records from 2011 to 2020, combined with the SAFRAN 8 km atmospheric analysis grid (Pimont et al, 2021; Vidal et al., 2010). Ignitions were aggregated within each SAFRAN

grid cell (8 km × 8 km), and a relative ignition probability was assigned to each cell based on the observed frequency of fire starts over the 10-year period.

This method follows a common approach in large-scale fire modelling, where ignition likelihood is spatially distributed according to past ignition patterns, normalized by fixed atmospheric grid cells to ensure consistency across meteorological inputs. The resulting ignition layer therefore represents:

- a spatially explicit ignition probability derived from historical ignition density,
- mapped at a 8 km resolution
- then interpolated to the 30m simulation grid used in BURN-P3+, ensuring compatibility with fuel and topographic layers.

Both human-caused and natural (lightning) ignitions were considered for this grid, though the former dominate in southwestern France, accounting for approximately 90–94% of wildfire ignitions in the Landes de Gascogne region (CRPF Nouvelle-Aquitaine, 2017). These ignition probability rasters were included as inputs to BURN-P3+ to control the spatial distribution of simulated fire starts.

A limitation of this approach is that historical ignition patterns reflect past human activities and suppression efficiency, which may not fully represent future ignition potential under evolving land-use and climatic conditions.

Weather input

Meteorological inputs were produced using fire danger indices from the Canadian Fire Weather Index (FWI) System (Van Wagner, 1987; Wotton, 2009), including both moisture codes (FFMC, DMC, DC) and fire behavior indices (ISI, BUI, FWI).

Data sources and processing

- Daily temperature, humidity, precipitation and wind data were obtained from Copernicus ERA5 reanalysis.
- The FWI System indices were computed using the R package *cffdrs* (Wang et al., 2017).

- Daily FWI values were aggregated within predefined weather zones, established from long-term climatology rather than from 2022-only data, consistent with recommendations from the Canadian FFDRS framework (Wotton et al., 2022).

These weather inputs were used to:

- construct the three fire weather scenarios (Moderate, High, Extreme)
- generate lists of hourly propagation conditions stratified by season and weather zone

These data were used to construct fire weather scenarios that reflect the most critical meteorological drivers of wildfire behaviour, including prolonged drought, high temperatures, and extreme wind conditions. To ensure spatial consistency in the simulations, predefined weather zones established based on long-term climatic patterns rather than single-year data were used to calibrate fire behaviour parameters across the study area.

Tabular inputs to the simulation include data on seasonal classes provided by SDIS40 and SDIS33 and analysis of meteorological data. The seasons are classified into three main periods and curing values were derived from expert knowledge and reflect typical biomass dryness and availability across the year (Parisien et al., 2018)

Seasonal structure and curing values

Table 3. Description of seasonal inputs used in BURNP3+

Season	Calendar period	Median Julian day	Curing (%)
Early Spring	15 February - 14 May	90	80%
Late Spring	15 May - 14 August	181	55%
Summer	15 August - 15 October	258	65%

These seasonal curing values are applied uniformly across the landscape to reflect typical fine fuel availability before the main fire season, during the core summer period, and in late-fire-season conditions.

Spread-day events

For each simulated fire, BURN-P3+ assigns a “spread-day event” category, determining the number of consecutive days with hazardous fire weather. This approach follows the probabilistic structure commonly used in the Prometheus fire spread system. Three fire weather severity classes were used, each defined by the proportion of 1-day to multi-day adverse weather sequences :

Table 4. Description of Spread-day events probability distributions per climatic scenario

Event severity	1-day	2-day	3-day	4-day	5-day
Moderate	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%
High	95%	2%	2%	1%	0%
Extreme	90%	5%	2%	2%	1%

Fire probability of burning assesement

The assessment of wildfire hazard in this study was built upon burn probability (BP) and. This parameter was used to construct wildfire hazard maps, which combine spatially explicit fire risk data with local landscape characteristics. BP quantifies the likelihood of occurrent under varying weather and landscape conditions which influences firefighting strategies. Burn probability was derived from the fire weather and landscape data, adjusted for historical ignition patterns. The hazard maps resulting from these calculations provide a comprehensive view of the spatial distribution of fire hazard.

Fire risk assessment

While fire hazard assessment provides insights into the likelihood of wildfire spread, a complete wildfire risk evaluation requires integrating exposure and sensitivity factors (Scott et al., 2013; Chuvieco et al., 2014). In this study, we define fire risk as the interaction between wildfire hazard and potential impacts on human infrastructure, following the general formulation (Hardy, 2005):

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Hazard} \times \text{Exposure}$$

Where Hazard is derived from BURN-P3 simulations under extreme fire weather scenarios and exposure is based on the presence of vulnerable elements, in this case, urban areas, as identified in spatial datasets.

This approach aligns with the conceptual models of wildfire risk developed by Finney (2005), where fire spread likelihood is combined with asset exposure to guide risk-informed decision-making.

We quantify fire risk by integrating fire hazard metrics with urban exposure, following methodologies from previous wildfire risk assessments (Miller & Ager, 2013; San-Miguel-Ayanz et al., 2017) :

- High-risk areas correspond to areas where high burn probability coincides with dense urban zones, requiring urgent mitigation actions.
- Moderate-risk areas include areas with moderate fire hazard near settlements, where preventative strategies (e.g., fuel reduction) could lower risk.
- Low-risk areas are either fire-prone but sparsely populated or urban but less exposed to fire spread.

This classification provides actionable insights for landscape-scale fire prevention planning, particularly in prioritizing fuel treatments, firebreaks, and resource allocation for firefighting services (Ager et al., 2021). By incorporating risk mapping, this study contributes to a growing body of research advocating for spatially explicit wildfire risk assessment as a basis for integrated fire management policies (Moritz et al., 2014; Bowman et al., 2020).

Results

This figure presents the spatial distribution of burn probability obtained from 20,000 BURN-P3+ simulations across three climatic scenarios (“Moderate” 1991–2020, “High” 2021–2022, and “Extreme” 2041–2070). For each scenario, results are shown for both the untreated (current) and treated (modified) landscape structures. The maps highlight how burn probability increases with climatic severity, with larger portions of the landscape being intersected by fire perimeters under more extreme conditions. High-probability zones align with areas dominated by highly flammable fuel types—including immature maritime pine stands (C4)—which consistently act as propagation hotspots.

The comparison between untreated and treated configurations further reveals how the introduction of regional-scale fuel discontinuities reduces the spatial extent and connectivity of these high-probability areas, particularly under extreme climate.

Figure 3. Burn Probability across the study area under “Moderate”, “High”, and “Extreme” climatic scenarios for untreated and treated landscape structures

This figure 4 shows the difference in burn probability between each scenario and its respective baseline (1991–2020 “Moderate” scenario), highlighting where fire activity is expected to increase or decrease under future climatic conditions. Positive values indicate higher burn probability relative to baseline, while negative values illustrate rare areas where probability decreases due to stochastic modelling effects. Both “High” and “Extreme” scenarios show widespread increases in burn probability, reflecting more fire-conducive weather. Differences are more pronounced in regions containing C4 fuels, where climatic stress amplifies the likelihood of repeated fire spread. When comparing untreated and treated landscapes, the treated configuration displays reduced

amplitude and continuity of burn probability increases, demonstrating that strategically reorganizing non-combustible areas into regional discontinuities mitigates the projected intensification of wildfire activity, even under extreme climate conditions.

Figure 4. Differences in burn probability relative to the baseline scenario for “High” and “Extreme” climatic scenarios, for untreated and treated landscape structures

Discussion

Across the baseline landscape configuration, burn probability increases consistently from the Moderate to the High and Extreme climatic scenarios. Because BURN-P3+ operates by simulating 20,000 fire spread events per scenario, the rise in burn probability directly reflects the strengthening of fire-conductive conditions represented by the Fire Weather Index (FWI). Higher FWI values intensify wind-driven spread, reduce fine-fuel moisture, and increase flame length, processes explicitly described in the components of the FWI system (NWCG, n.d.), resulting in simulated fire perimeters intersecting a greater proportion of the landscape.

This gradient is coherent with previous research showing that climatic severity is the dominant regulator of fire spread potential in continuous pine-dominated systems (Ruffault et al., 2020; Pimont et al., 2021). In the structurally homogeneous Landes de Gascogne, stronger climatic forcing produces more persistent and spatially coherent corridors of fire propagation, which are expressed clearly in the burn probability maps.

At 30-m resolution, the simulations reveal that the highest burn probability values are concentrated in areas dominated by combustible type C4 (immature maritime pine stands aged 1 to 25 years). These fuel types are characterized by high horizontal continuity, elevated fine-fuel load, and high responsiveness under dry conditions.

BURN-P3+ correctly reproduces this behaviour: repeated intersection of simulated perimeters with C4 pixels generates persistent hotspots of burn probability. These results are consistent with empirical observations in the Landes, where young pine stands are among the most flammable strata during late-season droughts due to their dense fine-fuel structure and rapid ignition potential (Dupuy et al., 2009).

In effect, C4 patches act as regional propagation engines, shaping the geography of high burn probability across all climatic scenarios.

The edited scenario maintains the same overall ratio of forest to non-combustible areas but reorganizes the geometry of non-combustible zones to create regional fuel discontinuities. This structural adjustment, without reducing productive forest area, produces a modification of burn probability patterns.

Although hotspots associated with C4 fuels remain detectable, they become spatially smaller, more fragmented, and less connected than in the baseline landscape. The reconfigured discontinuities interrupt long-distance fire spread pathways, reducing the coherence of high-probability corridors.

This effect becomes particularly evident under the Extreme climatic scenario: despite substantially harsher conditions, the number and spatial continuity of high-probability zones decrease relative to the baseline. These results reinforce recent findings showing that the spatial configuration of fuel breaks matters more than their total area when climatic severity increases (Parisien et al., 2019).

Thus, altering fuel continuity at regional scale can systematically weaken the landscape's capacity to sustain fast-moving fires, even under extreme fire weather.

The use of 20,000 simulated fire events per scenario ensures that the burn probability surfaces are statistically robust. Because burn probability in BURN-P3+ corresponds to the number of times a pixel is crossed by a simulated fire perimeter, high iteration numbers reduce stochastic effect and clarify deterministic structural patterns such as those driven by C4 fuels or by landscape discontinuities.

This simulation density is particularly important for interpreting differences among scenarios: the observed contrasts reflect meaningful landscape-level processes rather than random variability inherent to probabilistic fire spread modeling.

The results show that the current landscape configuration, dominated by large, continuous blocks of maritime pine facilitates long-distance fire spread when climatic conditions deteriorate. However, the edited scenario demonstrates that reorganizing non-combustible areas into coherent discontinuities can significantly reduce burn probability patterns without diminishing the total forested area.

These findings suggest that fuel management strategies focused on spatial layout, rather than solely on fuel reduction, could meaningfully enhance the regional fire resilience of the Landes massif. This aligns with the growing body of literature emphasising landscape-scale connectivity management as a critical lever for mitigating fire spread potential (Beverly & McLoughlin, 2021).

Targeting C4-dominated areas, identified here as key propagation hotspots, may further increase the effectiveness of such interventions, particularly as climate-driven extremes become more frequent.

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Weather Zones

Figure A. Spatial delineation of weather zones for Burn-P3+ Inputs